

Composition and Seasonal Variation of Phytoplankton in Lotus Pond of Jahangirnagar University Campus, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Phytoplankton are crucial for aquatic ecosystem playing significant role in primary production and vital component of microorganism's community as well. The present investigation was carried out to monitor the species composition, density (PD), seasonal variation in diversity and season wise dominant taxa of the selected pond named as Lotus Pond during the period of June, 2020 to May, 2021. A total of 69 taxa comprising 33 genera belonging to 15 orders under 7 classes were recorded. Seasonal changes in phytoplankton community with their individual density were studied. The total density of phytoplankton community was recorded $177.65 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$, $104.13 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$, $74.8 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$ and $19.13 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$ during summer, monsoon autumn and winter respectively. The range of density of individual phytoplankton varied from $0.85 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$ to $76.97 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$ (*Trachelomonas*). Dominant phytoplankton of four seasons in the selected pond were studied. In summer, dominant phytoplankton was *Actinastrum* ($74.37 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$), in monsoon, *Trachelomonas* ($36.98 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$), while in autumn *Synedra* ($25.5 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$), and in winter it was *Trachelomonas* ($7.65 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$). According to Shannon diversity index, the selected pond was found moderately diverse throughout the study period and the index ranged from 1.82 (monsoon) to 2.33 (winter).

Keywords: *Phytoplankton, density, seasonal variation, dominant species and Shannon-Weiner index.*

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Introduction

Wetlands consist of rich biodiversity of flora and fauna important for local, national and regional significance (Bhuiyan et al., 2010). Among the plankton community of aquatic ecosystems (both marine and freshwater), phytoplankton, the autotrophic components play the most significant role in primary production and form the first trophic level of the food chain. Qualitative and quantitative studies of phytoplankton can assess the water quality of any water bodies. As the primary producer, phytoplankton population (Mollah and Haque, 1978) determine the status of whole aquatic community.

Due to their ubiquitous presence in all kind of habitats (lakes, rivers, ponds, seas, oceans, moist surface, stone, snow etc.) they are considered as cosmopolitan in nature. High diversity of phytoplankton can be found in fertile standing water bodies that may changes according to the variation of silica and other nutrients (Egge et al., 1992 and Chellappa et al., 2008).

On one hand, phytoplankton act as purifiers of air and water while on the other side they able to pollute water bodies. Since any effect on the lower level of food chain has the consequence to the higher level,

phytoplankton can determine the impact of any toxic chemicals on the aquatic ecosystem (Joubert, 1980). Phytoplankton are used as a tool for determining pollution in water as indicator microorganisms (Trivedy and Goel, 1984; Sudhaker et al., 1994; Dwivedi and Pandey, 2002).

Identification and biodiversity assessment of phytoplankton may play great role in the conservation of aquatic system (Gowsami, 2012).

Phytoplankton vary considerably in distribution with respect to different seasons and pollution load. To determine the biodiversity of a given aquatic ecosystem, the composition study of phytoplankton may play a key role for the environment researches. The study on composition and seasonal variation of 'Lotus Pond' remain undiscovered; therefore, the present assessment was under consideration to document the composition algal flora along with their density, dominancy and seasonal variation.

Materials and Methods

Study Site and Period

The Lotus Pond is located in Jahangirnagar University campus, which is situated about 32 km west of Dhaka city in Savar thana of Dhaka district. The relative position of study sites is latitude $90^{\circ}13' N$ and longitude $23^{\circ}51' E$. The studied water body is triangular in shape, medium in size, its source of nutrient is washing away rain water, no pisciculture practices and vegetation is dominated by Lotus flower. The present study was conducted during the period from May, 2020 to May, 2021.

Photograph 1. Lotus Pond

Figure 1. Location of Lotus Pond

In situ Sample Collection

Collection of phytoplankton samples:

The sampling was carried out in the littoral zone of the lake from 10.00 am. - 3.00 pm. An integrated water sample from 50 cm depth was collected each time by a Schindler's Sampler (5 L capacity) from the three studied stations stn-1, stn-2 and stn-3. At first the sampler was dipped slowly under water to 50 cm depth and then closed by applying a jerking pull from the above. After confirming the closure of the sampler, it was taken out and the water was decanted in a black plastic carboy (5 L capacity) followed by the transportation to the laboratory for further analysis.

Sedimentation of sample and counting of phytoplankton density

In a plastic bottle of 1 liter capacity, sample water from study site were separately poured and fixed with Lugol's iodine solution and kept undisturbed in the dark for at least 48 h in order to facilitate sedimentation.

Enumeration of phytoplankton

Enumeration of phytoplankton was done under a compound microscope (Nikon SE) at a magnification of 10×40 with the help of the Hilbert Bacteria Counting Cell (Single round, Hawksly, UK). The Helber Bacteria Counting Cell looks just like a glass slide and is 50 mm long, 20 mm wide and 1mm thick. A microscopic circular counting chamber with engraved grids at the center of the slide surface. The total volume of the chamber is $1.005 \mu\text{l}$. The counting was carried out by putting one drop of well mixed phytoplankton sample on the counting chamber (HBCC) and a coverslip was put on it. Before counting HBCC cell was let stand for at least 1 minute to settle down phytoplankton. Phytoplankton present in the bottom of the HBCC cell was the counter. All the cells present was counted and the dominant group was identified. The counting was done in triplicate for each sample. Finally, the cell density of the phytoplankton was calculated per liter water by using the following formula.

$$\text{Density/l} = [\text{units}/3.015\mu\text{l} \times \{(10000 \div 3.015)\} \times (50 \div 9.7)] \div 100 \quad (1)$$

Where,

Units/3.015 μl = sum of the counts in triplicate of the phytoplankton individuals for each sample made by Hawkleys Counting Chamber, 3.015 μl = vol. of the Hawkleys Chamber (1.005×3) in μl .

10000 = 10 ml sub-sample of phytoplankton concentrate as obtained after passing of sample water through plankton net, in μl .

50 = Volumes of phytoplankton concentrate, in ml obtained after filtering 100 liter of sample water through plankton net.

9.7 = Actual vol. of phytoplankton concentrates obtained as a sub-sample fixed with 0.3 ml Lugol's solution ($9.7 + 0.3$) finally making a volume of 10 ml as supplied to us for counting.

100 = Amounts of sample water passed through plankton net in liters.

Qualitative analysis of phytoplankton

Before counting of the phytoplankton individual, a random checking of the sedimented phytoplanktonic material was carried out under high magnification for identification up to the species level. For identification, algal literatures as well as publications available for Bangladesh, other world monographs and books have been consulted (Smith 1950, Skuja 1956, Desikachary 1959, Starmach 1966, Islam and Begum 1970, Islam and Khondker 1981, Germain 1981, Prescott 1982, Huber-Pestalozzi 1955, 1961, 1968, 1983; Dillard 1989a, Yamagishi 1998, Ling and Tyler 2000, Islam and Alfasane 2002, 2004; Siddiqui *et al.* 2007, Begum, 2008, 2009; Ahmed *et al.* 2008, 2009; Khondker *et al.* 2007, 2008, 2009).

Calculation of diversity index

The equation for the Shannon-Weiner (1949) index:

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^s p_i \ln p_i \quad (2)$$

In the Shannon index, p is the proportion (n/N) of individuals of one particular species found (n) divided by the total number of individuals found (N), \ln is the natural log, Σ is the sum of the calculations, and s is the number of species.

Results and Discussion

Composition of Phytoplankton

Percentage of Classes

In the present investigation, 69 species under 33 genera were recorded belonged to 7 classes from the studied pond. Among them, 1 order, 1 genus and 2 species belong to Cyanophyceae, 5 orders, 14 genera and 26 species from Chlorophyceae, 5 orders, 10 genera and 23 species belonged to Bacillariophyceae, 1 order, 4 genus and 14 species belong to Euglenophyceae, 2 orders, 2 genera and 2 species from Cryptophyceae, 1 order 1 genus and 1 species belong to Xanthophyceae and 1 order, 1 genus and 2 species belong to Dinophyceae. (Table 1, 2, 3, 4 & 5).

At the Generic level percentage composition shows that Chlorophyceae dominates the studied sites and occupied 50%, followed by Bacillariophyceae (20%), Cyanophyceae (12.86%), Euglenophyceae (8.57%), Cryptophyceae (5.71%), Dinophyceae (1.43%) and Xanthophyceae (1.43%) respectively. (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Percentage of Classes at the Generic Level Recorded from the Lotus Pond

Figure 3. Percentage of Classes at the Species Level Recorded from the Lotus Pond

At the species level Chlorophyceae dominates the studied sites and occupied 43.28%, followed by Euglenophyceae (25.37%), Bacillariophyceae (16.42%), Cyanophyceae (8.96%), Cryptophyceae (4.48%), Dinophyceae (0.75%) and Xanthophyceae (0.75%) respectively (Fig. 3).

Phytoplankton community

Phytoplankton taxa were identified belonging to seven groups (Table 1 and Plate 1 to 3).

Cyanophyceae

During the study period, two species belonging to one genus *Oscillatoria* was found to compose Cyanophyceae (blue-green algae).

Chlorophyceae

Chlorophyceae ranked the first position in their abundance compared to other group of phytoplankton. In the present study 26 species under 14 genera were recorded. Among them *Chlamydomonas* was found to dominate with 5 species followed by *Tetraedron* (4 species) and *Closterium* (3 species).

Bacillariophyceae

Bacillariophyceae commonly known diatoms were found in second position among the other group of phytoplankton. During the study, 10 genera consisting 23 species were recorded. *Navicula* with 4 species was found to dominant among diatoms followed by *Pinnularia*, *Synedra*, *Nitzschia* and *Syndra* containing 3 species.

Euglenophyceae

During this study period 14 species under 4 genera under Euglenophyceae were recorded. The genera were *Euglena* (5 spp), *Phacus* (4 spp), *Trachelomonas* (3 spp) and *Lepocyclis* (2 spp).

Cryptophyceae

Two species under two genera *Chryptochrysis* and *Rhodomonas* were recorded in the present study. According to Islam and Khondker (1993) and Khondker and Chowdhury (1993), Cryptomonads (*Cryptomans ovate* and *Rhodomonas lacustris*) are very common in waters of Bangladesh.

Xanthophyceae

Cenritactus was the only taxon was recorded under Xanthophyceae.

Dinophyceae

The genus *Pridinium* containing 2 species was found in the class Dinophyceae. Begum and Hossain (1993) also reported the least representation of Dinophyceae of a pond at Demra, Dhaka.

A study in four aquaculture ponds of Bangladesh by Affan et al., 2005 found 45 phytoplankton in total, among them Cyanophyceae (30 spp.), Chlorophyceae (7 spp.), Bacillariophyceae (5 spp.) and Euglenophyceae (3 spp.) were identified. The pond of the present investigation was in natural condition without any agricultural practices that may be result in the less abundance of Cyanophyceae and more of Chlorophyceae. According to Hujare et al., (2008) In a fresh water tank of Maharashtra, percentage composition of each group of phytoplankton was found 35.77% of Cyanophyceae, 34% of Bacillariophyceae and Chlorophyceae ranked third position (27.4%). Khan et al., 2025 recorded a total of 15 phytoplankton species from the man-made Kaptai lake in Bnagladesh and reported that the phytoplankton community was dominated by Chlorophyceae (61.1%).

Seasonal percentage of classes in the studied site

According to Rashid (1991) four distinct seasons prevail in Bangladesh. These are: summer (March to May), monsoon (June to Early October), autumn (Late October to November) and winter (November to February). In the present study, Chlorophyceae was found to dominate in summer (65%), monsoon (38%) and winter season (40%), whether in autumn it was Bacillariophyceae (50%) (Fig. 4).

According to Affan et al., 2005 Chlorophyceae dominated monsoon, Cyanophyceae dominated the spring and early autumn, whereas Bacillariophyceae was dominant in winter and Euglenophyceae was dominant in late autumn in four different aquaculture ponds in Bangladesh.

Figure 4. Relative Percentage of All Classes Found in the Study Area

Table 1. List of Phytoplankton Taxa Recorded from the Lotus Pond

Genus	Species	Genus	Species
Class 1: Cyanophyceae			
<i>Oscillatoria</i>	<i>Oscillatoria irrigua</i> (Kütz.) Gomont	<i>Scenedesmus</i>	<i>Scenedesmus similagenus</i> Hortob.
	<i>Oscillatoria minnesotensis</i> Tilden		<i>Schroederia antillarum</i> Kom.
Class 2: Chlorophyceae			
<i>Actinastrum</i>	<i>Actinastrum hantzschii</i> Lagerheim	<i>Tetraedron</i>	<i>Tetraedron bifurcatum</i> (Wille) Lagerheim
<i>Chlamydomonas</i>	<i>Chlamydomonas pulchra</i> Skvortz.		<i>Tetraedron muticum</i> (A. Br.) Hansgirg
	<i>Chlamydomonas angulosa</i> Nyg.		<i>Tetraedron minimum</i> (A. Br.) Hansg.
	<i>Chlamydomonas gloeogama</i> Kors.	<i>Schroederia</i>	<i>Schroederia antillarum</i> Kom.
	<i>Chlamydomonas gloeopara</i> Rodhe et Skuja.		<i>Schroederia setigera</i> (Schröd.) Lemmermann
	<i>Chlamydomonas globosa</i> Snow	<i>Monoraphidium</i>	<i>Monoraphidium arcuatum</i> (Koršikov) Hind
<i>Coelastrum</i>	<i>Closterium limneticum</i> Lemm. fa.	<i>Pediastrum</i>	<i>Pediastrum tetras</i> var. <i>traedron</i> (Corda) Hansgirg
	<i>Chaetomorpha linum</i> (Müll.) Kütz. Phyc.	<i>Tetrasrum</i>	<i>Tetrastrum heteracanthum</i> (Nordst.) Chodat
<i>Characium</i>	<i>Characium ornithocephalum</i> A. Braun	<i>Crucigenia</i>	<i>Crucigenia quadrata</i> Morren
<i>Closterium</i>	<i>Closterium diana</i> var. <i>pseudodiana</i> (Roy) Krieger		<i>Crucigeniella crucifera</i> (Wolle) Komérek
	<i>Closterium intermedium</i> var. <i>hibernicum</i> West & West	<i>Dictyosphaerium</i>	<i>Dictyosphaerium granulatum</i> Hind.
<i>Crucigenia</i>	<i>Crucigenia quadrata</i> Morren		
<i>Hyaloraphidium</i>	<i>Hyaloraphidium contortum</i> Pascher & Koršikov		
Bacillariophyceae			
<i>Acanthes</i>	<i>Achnanthes minutissima</i> Kütz		<i>Synedra tabulata</i> (Ag.) Kützing
<i>Cyclotella</i>	<i>Cyclotella comta</i> var. <i>affinis</i> Grunow in Van Heurck		<i>Synedra ulna</i> (Nitzsch) Ehr.
	<i>Cyclotella comensis</i> Grunow in Van Heurck	<i>Fragillaria</i>	<i>Fragillaria capucina</i> Desm.
<i>Cymbella</i>	<i>Cymbella turgidula</i> Grun.		<i>Fragillaria crotonensis</i> Kitton

	<i>Cymbella gracilis</i> (Rabch.) Cl.	<i>Melosira</i>	<i>Melosira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> Müll
	<i>Cymbella parva</i> (W. Smith) Kirchner	Class 4: Euglenophyceae	
<i>Gomphonema</i>	<i>Gomphonema spaerophorum</i> Ehrenberg	<i>Euglena</i>	<i>Euglena alata</i> Thompson
	<i>Gomphonema augur</i> Ehr.		<i>Euglena oblonga</i> Schmitz
<i>Navicula</i>	<i>Navicula exigua</i> (Dujardin) Nouv.		<i>Euglena exilis</i> Gojdics
	<i>Navicula pupula</i> var. <i>capitata</i> Hust.		<i>Euglena bemichromata</i> Skuja
	<i>Navicula americana</i> Ehrenberg		<i>Euglena rostifera</i> Johnson
<i>Nitzschia</i>	<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i> (Kützing) W. Smith	<i>Lepocynclis</i>	<i>Lepocynclis teres</i> fa. <i>parvula</i> Conr.
	<i>Nitzschia alpine</i> (Näg) Hustedt		<i>Lepocynclis ovum</i> var. <i>bütschlii</i> (Lemm.) Conr.
	<i>Nitzschia fruticosa</i> Hust.	<i>Trachelomonas</i>	<i>Trachelomonas lacustris</i> Drez.
<i>Nitzschia linearis</i> W. Smith	<i>Trachelomonas planktonica</i> Swir.		
<i>Pinnularia</i>	<i>Pinnularia krookei</i> (Grun.) Cleve	<i>Phacus</i>	<i>Trachelomonas volvocina</i> Ehrenberg
	<i>Pinnularia major</i> (Kütz) Rabenhorst		<i>Phacus currucauda</i> Swirenko
	<i>Pinnularia pulchra</i> Østrup		<i>Phacus granum</i> Drez.
<i>Synedra</i>	<i>Synedra acus</i> Kütz.		<i>Phacus granum</i> Drez.
			<i>Phacus hamelii</i> Allorgae and Lafevre
		Class 5: Chryptophyceae	
		<i>Chryptochrysis</i>	<i>Chryptochrysis minor</i> Nygaard
		<i>Rhodomonas</i>	<i>Rhodomonas minuta</i> Skuja
Class 6. Xanthophyceae		Class 7: Dinophyceae	
<i>Centritractus</i>	<i>Centritractus belolonophorus</i> (Schmidle) Lammermann	<i>Peridinium</i>	<i>Peridinium aciculiferum</i> f. <i>inermis</i> Woloszyńska
			<i>Peridinium goslaviense</i> Wol.
Total Class: 7, Total genera: 33, Total species: 69			

Seasonal Changes in the Density of Phytoplankton in the Studied Pond

Depending upon the above-mentioned classification, seasonal changes in the composition of phytoplankton and their density were studied for the pond and presented in Table 2, Table 3, Table 4, & Table 5. The result showed the total highest density ($177.65 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$) was recorded during summer while the lowest overall density ($19.125 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$) of phytoplankton was found in winter that is similar to the study by Alam et al., (2020) in Ramsar lake, Bangladesh. Conversely, the present result is opposite to the findings by Al-Tae and Mahmoud (2023) in Sawa lake of Southern Iraq. According to their study, the highest phytoplankton density was recorded in winter ($495.03 \times 10^3 \text{ Indiv}/\text{L}$) while in the summer the lowest density of phytoplankton ($89.50 \times 10^3 \text{ Indiv}/\text{L}$).

In case of individual genus, the present study revealed that *Actinastrum* ($74.375 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$), *Trachelomonas* ($76.97 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$), *Synedra* ($25.5 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$) and *Trachelomonas* ($7.65 \text{ Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$) showed highest density during summer, rainy, autumn and winter season respectively.

According to Zinat et al., (2021), in Pasur River estuary of Bangladesh relatively higher cell density of phytoplankton was recorded during post-monsoon season ($48.204 \times 10^3 \text{ cells}/\text{L}$) and lower during monsoon season ($37.301 \times 10^3 \text{ cells}/\text{L}$).

Table 2. Density of Individual Phytoplankton (PD) in During Summer

Class	Order	No. of algae	Genus	PD ($\text{Ind} \times 10^4/\text{L}$)
Cyanophyceae	Oscillatoriales	1	<i>Oscillatoria</i>	12.75
Chlorophyceae	Sphaeropleales	7	<i>Coelastrum</i>	5.95
			<i>Characium</i>	11.9
			<i>Tetrasium</i>	3.4

			<i>Pediatrum</i>	0.85
			<i>Monoraphidium</i>	19.55
			<i>Scenedesmus</i>	11.9
			<i>Tetraedron</i>	1.7
	Chlorellales	2	<i>Actinastrum</i>	74.375
			<i>Dictyosphaerium</i>	1.7
	Chlamydomonadales	2	<i>Schroederia</i>	2.55
			<i>Pandorina</i>	0.85
	Desmidiaceae	1	<i>Closterium</i>	0.85
	Chlorococcales	2	<i>Crucigenia</i>	0.85
			<i>Hyaloraphidium</i>	11.05
Bacillariophyceae	Fragilariaceae	1	<i>Synedra</i>	2.55
Euglenophyta	Euglenales	3	<i>Euglena</i>	4.25
			<i>Phacus</i>	1.7
			<i>Trachlelomonas</i>	4.675
Cryptophyta	Cryptomonadales	1	<i>Cryptomonas</i>	2.55
	Pyrenomonadales	1	<i>Rhodomonas</i>	0.85
Dinophyceae	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Xanthophyta	Mischococcales	1	<i>Centritractus</i>	0.85
Total				177.65

Table 3. Density of Individual Phytoplankton (PD) during Monsoon

Class	Order	No. of algae	Genus	PD(Ind×10 ⁴ /L)
Cyanophyceae	Oscillatoriales	1	<i>Oscillatoria</i>	5.1
Chlorophyceae	Sphaeropleales	4	<i>Scenedesmus</i>	1.7
			<i>Characium</i>	0.85
			<i>Tetrastum</i>	0.85
			<i>Monoraphidium</i>	11.05
	Chlorellales	1	<i>Actinastrum</i>	5.1
Chlamydomonadales	2	<i>Schroederia</i>	3.4	
		<i>Chlamydomonas</i>	0.85	
Bacillariophyceae	Fragilariaceae	2	<i>Hyaloraphidium</i>	7.65
			<i>Fragillaria</i>	0.85
	Cymbellales	2	<i>Cymbella</i>	1.7
			<i>Gomphonema</i>	5.1
	Naviculales	1	<i>Pinnularia</i>	0.85
	Achnanthes	1	<i>Achnanthes</i>	2.55
	Thalassiosirales	1	<i>Melosira</i>	0.85
Euglenophyceae	Euglenales	3	<i>Euglena</i>	4.25
			<i>Lepocinclis</i>	0.85
			<i>Trachlelomonas</i>	36.975
Cryptophyceae	Cryptomonadales	1	<i>Cryptomonas</i>	4.25
	Pyrenomonadales	1	<i>Rhodomonas</i>	9.35
Total				104.125

Table 4. Density of Individual Phytoplankton (PD) during Autumn

Class	Order	No. of algae	Genus	PD (Ind×10 ⁴ /L)
Cyanophyta	Oscillatoriales	1	<i>Oscillatoria</i>	2.55
Chlorophyceae	Sphaeropleales	2	<i>Scenedesmus</i>	0.85
			<i>Monoraphidium</i>	0.85
	Chlamydomonadales	1	<i>Chlamydomonas</i>	0.85
Bacillariophyceae	Fragilariaceae	2	<i>Fragillaria</i>	3.4

			Synedra	25.5
	Cymbellales	1	<i>Cymbella</i>	3.4
	Naviculales	2	<i>Pinnularia</i>	3.4
			<i>Navicula</i>	17.0
	Achnanthes	1	<i>Achnanthes</i>	1.7
	Thalassiosirales	1	<i>Melosira</i>	3.4
Euglenophyceae	Euglenales	2	<i>Euglena</i>	1.7
			<i>Trachlelomonas</i>	6.8
Cryptophyceae	Cryptomonadales	1	<i>Cryptomonas</i>	3.4
Total				74.8

Table 5. Density of Individual Phytoplankton (PD) during Winter

Class	Order	No. of algae	Genus	PD (Ind×10 ⁴ /L)
Cyanophyta	Oscillatoriales	1	<i>Oscillatoria</i>	3.825
Chlorophyceae	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Bacillariophyceae	Bacillariales	1	<i>Nitzschia</i>	0.85
	Thalassiosirales	1	<i>Cyclotella</i>	0.425
Euglenophyceae	Euglenales	4	<i>Euglena</i>	1.275
			<i>Trachlelomonas</i>	7.65
			<i>Lepocinclis</i>	1.275
			<i>Phacus</i>	0.425
Cryptophyceae	Cryptomonadales	1	<i>Cryptomonas</i>	0.425
	Pyrenomonadales	1	<i>Rhodomonas</i>	2.125
Dinophyceae	Peridinales	1	<i>Peridinium</i>	0.85
Total				19.125

Dominant Phytoplankton and Their Density in Different Seasons

In the present study, during summer, dominant phytoplanktons were *Actinastrum* (74.37 Ind×10⁴/L), *Monoraphidium* (19.55 Ind×10⁴/L), *Oscillatoria* (12.75 Ind×10⁴/L) and *Scenedesmus* (11.9 Ind×10⁴/L) during summer season. In monsoon, *Trachelomonas* (36.98 Ind×10⁴/L), *Monoraphidium* (11.05 Ind×10⁴/L), *Cryptomonas* (9.35) Ind×10⁴/L and *Hyaloraphidium* (7.65 Ind×10⁴/L) were dominant while in autumn *Synedra* (25.5 Ind×10⁴/L), *Pinnularia* (17 Ind×10⁴/L), *Trachelomonas* (6.8 Ind×10⁴/L) and *Fragilaria* (3.4 Ind×10⁴/L) dominated the pond. In winter, dominating genera were *Trachelomonas* (7.65 Ind×10⁴/L), *Oscillatoria* (3.83 Ind×10⁴/L), *Rhodomonas* (2.13 Ind×10⁴/L) and *Euglena* (1.28 Ind×10⁴/L) (Table 6). Habib, et al., (1991) mentioned *Pediastrum* as the most abundant followed by *Scenedesmus*, *Volvox*, *Chlorella*, *Ankistrodesmus* and *Closterium*, while Vyas and Kumar, (1968) recorded *Ulothrix* to be the most dominant genus followed by *Pediastrum*, *Closterium*, *Chlorella*, *Volvox* and *Ankistrodesmus*. In another study, Habib et al., (1991) stated that *Synedra* was the most dominant followed by *Navicula* and *Cyclotella*. Ali et al., (1985a) pointed that *Phacus* was the most dominant followed by *Euglena*.

Table 6. Density of Dominant Phytoplankton in Different Seasons

Season	Dominant-1	Dominant 2	Dominant 3	Dominant 4	Total Dominant (Ind×10 ⁴ /L)	Others Ind×10 ⁴ /L	Total phytoplankton density (Ind×10 ⁴ /L)
Summer	<i>Actinastrum</i> 74.37	<i>Monoraphidium</i> <i>m</i> 19.55	<i>Oscillatoria</i> 12.75	<i>Scenedesmus</i> 11.9	118.57	59.05	177.65
Rainy	<i>Trachelomonas</i> <i>s</i>	<i>Monoraphidium</i> <i>m</i>	<i>Cryptomonas</i> 9.35	<i>Hyaloraphidium</i> <i>m</i>	65.03	39.10	104.13

	36.98	11.05		7.65			
Autumn	<i>Synedra</i> 25.5	<i>Pinnularia</i> 17	<i>Trachelomonas</i> 6.8	<i>Fragillaria</i> 3.4	52.7	22.1	74.8
Winter	<i>Trachelomonas</i> 7.65	<i>Oscillatoria</i> 3.83	<i>Rhodomonas</i> 2.13	<i>Euglena</i> 1.28	14.89	4.24	19.13

Statistical Analysis

Shannon diversity index (H')

Shannon diversity index is commonly used to characterize species diversity in a community. According to most ecological research, it typically ranges from 1.5 to 3.5 though there is technical range from 0 (zero diversity) to greater than 4.0 of 5.0 (exceptionally diverse). Higher values indicate greater species richness and higher evenness in species

In the present research, according to the Shannon diversity index, the selected water body was low to moderately diverse at the genus level throughout the year. The highest diversity was found in monsoon (2.33) and the lowest one (1.82) was in winter season (Fig. 5). The value generally indicates that the water body was in mesotrophic or lightly eutrophic condition.

Figure 5. Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index (at genus level) for the Phytoplankton of the Studied Pond

In a lake or water body, the low Shannon-Wiener diversity index values of phytoplankton suggest that the water body is in a higher trophic state (Jekatierynczuk-Rudczyk et al., 2014; Cai et al., 2022). Eutrophic and mesotrophic water bodies provide high biodiversity indices where one or two dominant species dominate the phytoplankton community.

<i>Oscillatoria irrigua</i>	<i>Oscillatoria minnesotensis</i>	<i>Actinastrum bantzschii</i>	<i>Chlamydomonas pulchra</i>
<i>Chlamydomonas angulosa</i>	<i>Chlamydomonas gloeogama</i>	<i>Chlamydomonas</i> sp.	<i>Pediastrum tetras</i> var. <i>tetraedron</i>
<i>Hyaloraphidium contortum</i>	<i>Tetrastrum heterocanthum</i>	<i>Tetraedron bifurcatum</i>	<i>Tetraedron muticum</i>
<i>Cyclotella comta</i>	<i>Cymbella turgidula</i>	<i>Synedra acus</i>	<i>Fragillaria capucina</i>

Plate 1. Microscopic Images of the Identified Phytoplankton from Lotus Pond

<i>Navicula exigua</i>	<i>Navicula americana</i>	<i>Nitzschia alpine</i>	<i>Melosira granulata</i>
<i>Gomphonema augur</i>	<i>Euglena exilis</i>	<i>Euglena rostrifera</i>	<i>Euglena alata</i>
<i>Euglena hemichromatata</i>	<i>Euglena oblonga</i>	<i>Lepocinclis ovum</i> var. <i>butschlii</i>	<i>Trachelomonas lacutris</i>
<i>Trachelomonas volvocina</i>	<i>Trachelomonas lismorensis</i>	<i>Phacus curvicauda</i>	<i>Phacus granum</i>

Plate 2. Microscopic Images of the Identified Phytoplankton from Lotus Pond

Plate 3. Microscopic Images of the Identified Phytoplankton from Lotus Pond

Conclusion

The studied water body very important for ecosystem of the Jahangirnagar University campus. The value of Shannon diversity index of phytoplankton generally indicates that the water body was in mesotrophic or lightly eutrophic condition. Analysis and interpretation of the data on phytoplankton provided the necessary information to assess the impact of tourism related activities on the quality of the water bodies. Recorded data from this research would be helpful in planning for future policy decisions on using the reservoir center as well as in the better conservation and management of the precious wildlife in the world-famous sanctuary. It would also be helpful in documenting the list of phytoplankton community of the water bodies in the campus.

References

- Affan, A., Jewel, A. S., Haque, M., Khan, S., & Lee, J.-B. (2005). Seasonal cycle of phytoplankton in aquaculture ponds in Bangladesh. *Algae*, 20(1), 43–52.
- Alam, M. R., Eliyana, M. N. A., Touhiduzzaman, S. M., & Hossain, M. N. (2020). Diversity and seasonal variation of plankton community in Ramsagar Lake, Bangladesh. *Discovery Agriculture*, 6(16), 199–209.
- Ali, M. M., Islam, M. A., Habib, M. A. B., & Rahmatullah, S. M. (1985). Effect of meteorological and some physico-chemical factors of water on the growth of phytoplankton in a pond. *Bangladesh Journal of Aquaculture*, 6–7(1), 1–10.
- Al-Tae, I., & Mahmoud, A. (2023). Measurement of some biodiversity indices for phytoplankton community in Sawa Lake, Southern Iraq. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Biology and Fisheries*, 27(6), 1043–1055.
- Begum, Z. N. T. (2008). A taxonomic account on the phytoplankton of a pond receiving textile industrial effluents. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 15(2), 129–139.
- Begum, Z. N. T. (2009). A taxonomic account on the phytoplankton of a pond receiving textile industrial effluents II: Euglenophyceae and Bacillariophyceae. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 16(1), 9–19.
- Begum, Z. N. T., & Hussain, M. Z. (1993). Phytoplankton of a pond in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Botany*, 22(1), 59–65.
- Bhuiyan, M. A. H., Khondker, M., & Begum, Z. N. (2010). Diversity in the pelagic plankton of wetland Ashulia. *Journal of Taxonomy and Biodiversity Research*, 4, 9–16.

- Cai, Y., Qi, L., Shan, T., Liu, Y., Zhang, N., Lu, X., & Fan, Y. (2022). Application of phytoplankton taxonomic α -diversity indices to assess trophic states in barrier lake: A case of Jingpo Lake. *Diversity*, 14(11), 1003. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d14111003>
- Chellappa, N. T., Borba, J. M., & Rocha, O. (2008). Phytoplankton community and physical-chemical characteristics of water in the public reservoir of Cruzeta, RN, Brazil. *Brazilian Journal of Biology*, 68(3), 477–494. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1519-69842008000300005>
- Dillard, G. E. (1989). *Freshwater algae of the southeastern United States: Part 1. Chlorophyceae: Volvocales, Tetrasporales and Chlorococcales* (Bibliotheca Phycologica, Vol. 81). J. Cramer.
- Dwivedi, B. K., & Pandey, G. C. (2002). Physicochemical factors and algal diversity of two ponds (Girija Kund and Maqubara Pond), Faizabad. *Pollution Research*, 21(3), 361–370.
- Egge, J. K., & Aksnes, D. L. (1992). Silicate as regulating nutrient in phytoplankton competition. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 83(2–3), 281–289. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps083281>
- Germain, H. (1981). *Flore des diatomées: Diatomophycées*. Société Nouvelle des Éditions Boubée.
- Goswami, H. K. (2012). Let us minimize global warming impacts by multidisciplinary approach. *Bionature*, 32, 51–69.
- Habib, M. A. B., Zaman, M. M., Hassan, M. R., & Rahman, M. S. (1991). Monthly fluctuation of phytoplankton and their relation with some physico-chemical parameters. *Bangladesh Journal of Agriculture*, 16, 43–53.
- Huber-Pestalozzi, G. H. (1955). *Das Phytoplankton des Süßwassers: Systematik und Biologie. Teil 4: Euglenophyceen*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- Huber-Pestalozzi, G. H. (1961). *Das Phytoplankton des Süßwassers: Systematik und Biologie. 5. Teil: Chlorophyceae (Grünalgen), Ordnung: Volvocales*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- Huber-Pestalozzi, G. H. (1968). *Das Phytoplankton des Süßwassers: Systematik und Biologie. 3. Teil: Cryptophyceae, Chloromonadophyceae, Dinophyceae*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- Huber-Pestalozzi, G. H. (1983). *Das Phytoplankton des Süßwassers: Systematik und Biologie. 7. Teil: 1. Hälfte Chlorophyceae*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- Hujare, M. S. (2008). Seasonal variations of phytoplankton in the freshwater tank of Talsande, Maharashtra. *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology*, 7(2), 253–256.
- Islam, A. K. M. N., & Alfasane, M. A. (2002). Euglenophyceae from Barisal district, Bangladesh: I. Genus *Phacus*. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 9(2), 3–18.
- Islam, A. K. M. N., & Alfasane, M. A. (2004). Euglenophyceae from Barisal district, Bangladesh: III. Genus *Trachelomonas* Ehr. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 11(2), 33–38.
- Islam, A. K. M. N., & Begum, Z. N. T. (1970). Studies on the phytoplankton of Dacca district. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Pakistan*, 15, 227–271.
- Islam, A. K. M. N., & Khondker, M. (1981). Euglenophyta of Bangladesh I. Genus *Trachelomonas*. *Internationale Revue der gesamten Hydrobiologie*, 66(1), 109–125. <https://doi.org/10.1002/iroh.19810660108>
- Islam, A. K. M. N., & Khondker, M. (1993). Some unicellular flagellate algae from Bangladesh. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh (Science)*, 19(2), 75–79.
- Jekatierynczuk-Rudczyk, E., Zieliński, P., Grabowska, M., Ejsmont-Karabin, J., Karpowicz, M., & Więcko, A. (2014). The trophic status of Suwalki Landscape Park lakes based on selected parameters

(NE Poland). *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 186(8), 5101–5121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-3750-5>

Joubert, G. (1980). *Trachelomonas* (Euglenophyceae) from the Pretoria Salt Pan. *Water SA*, 6(1), 1–10.

Khan, M. S., Monir, K. M. S., Nupur, F., Milon, A. I., Himel, I. A., Sarkar, A., Shimul, S. A., Nahid, S. A., & Rana, S. (2025). Assessment of plankton dynamics of Kaptai Lake, Bangladesh: Insights on the largest manmade lake ecosystems in Southeast Asia. *Helicon*, 11(15), e43920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.helicon.2025.e43920>

Khan, M. S., Monir, K. M. S., Nupur, F., Milon, A. I., Himel, I. A., Sarkar, A., Shimul, A. A., Nahid, S. A., & Rana, S. (2025). Assessment of plankton dynamics of Kaptai Lake, Bangladesh: Insights on the largest manmade lake ecosystems in Southeast Asia. *Helicon*, 11(15), e43920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.helicon.2025.e43920>

Khondker, M., & Chowdhury, A. M. (1993). Phytoplankton primary production in a tropical highly eutrophic lake. *Bangladesh Journal of Botany*, 22(2), 151–162.

Ling, H. U., & Tyler, P. A. (2000). *Australian freshwater algae (exclusive of diatoms)* (Bibliotheca Phycologica, Vol. 105). J. Cramer.

Mollah, M. F. A., & Haque, A. K. M. A. (1978). Studies on the phytoplankton of the River Karnafully, Chittagong. *Bangladesh Journal of Zoology*, 6(2), 79–91.

Prescott, G. W. (1982). *Algae of the western Great Lakes area*. Otto Koeltz Science Publishers.

Shannon, C. E., & Weaver, W. (1949). *The mathematical theory of communication*. University of Illinois Press.

Siddiqui, K. U., Ahmed, M. A., Ahmed, Z. U., Begum, Z. N. T., Hassan, M. A., Khondker, M., Kabir, S. M. H., Ahmed, M., Ahmed, A. T. A., Rahman, A. K. A., & Haque, E. U. (Eds.). (2007). *Encyclopedia of flora and fauna of Bangladesh: Vol. 2. Cyanobacteria, bacteria and fungi*. Asiatic Society of Bangladesh.

Skuja, H. (1956). Taxonomische und biologische Studien über das Phytoplankton schwedischer Binnengewässer. *Nova Acta Regiae Societatis Scientiarum Upsaliensis*, 16(3), 1–404.

Smith, G. M. (1950). *The freshwater algae of the United States* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.

Sudhakar, G., Jyothi, B., & Venkateswarlu, V. (1994). Role of diatoms as indicators of pollution in River Tungabhadra, South India. *Acta Hydrobiologica*, 36(1), 67–77.

Trivedy, R. K., & Goel, P. K. (1986). *Chemical and biological methods for water pollution studies*. Environmental Publications.

Vyas, L. N., & Kumar, H. D. (1968). Studies on the phytoplankton and other algae of Indrasagar tank, Udaipur, India. *Hydrobiologia*, 31(3–4), 421–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00019378>

Yamagishi, T. (1998). *Guide book to photomicrographs of the freshwater algae*. Uchida Rokakuho.

Zinat, A., Jewel, M. A. S., Khatun, B., Nayan, M. K. H., & Jasmine, S. (2021). Seasonal variations of phytoplankton community structure in Pasur River estuary of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies*, 9(3), 37–44.

